

Goldbach 1

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1 Introduction

This article is a response to Dorostanian, Amin. "A Proof of Goldbach's Conjecture." arXiv:1905.08033, May 2019.

This article discusses a set-theoretical approach to Goldbach's conjecture and outlines a proof structure for its validity. The author starts by formalizing the previous even cases as an inductive base, assuming the conjecture is true for even numbers smaller than $2k$. They then define a set of shifted primes, S_{2k} , which consists of pairs of prime numbers whose sum is $2k$. The author argues that this set is non-empty based on the inductive base.

Next, the author constructs a complement set, C_{2k} , which consists of pairs where one or both of the numbers are non-prime. They argue that this complement set should not intersect with S_{2k} .

The author then introduces a counting argument, stating that the total number of locations from shifted prime pairs exceeds the total number of locations available for $2k$. They express this as $|S_{2k}| \geq \Delta P_{2k}$, where ΔP_{2k} is the count of all shifted prime pairs inherited from prior verified cases up to $2k - 2$.

Using reductio ad absurdum, the author assumes that S_{2k} is empty, leading to a contradiction with the computed ΔP_{2k} , which guarantees the presence of prime pairs. This contradiction implies that S_{2k} must be non-empty.

Finally, the author concludes that by demonstrating the non-emptiness of S_{2k} for any chosen $2k$, and assuming the inductive hypothesis that the conjecture holds for all previous cases, Goldbach's conjecture must hold for $2k$ as well.

The article acknowledges the need for rigorous verification and confirmation through publication and peer-review within the mathematical community. It also provides references to related works on Goldbach's conjecture and prime numbers.

Overall, this article presents a logical framework for addressing Goldbach's conjecture and provides a potential path towards proving its validity.

2 Cases

1. Formalize Previous Even Cases (Inductive Base) Using the method described in the document, we establish an inductive base by assuming Goldbach's con-

jecture is true for all even numbers smaller than $2k$. By this inductive hypothesis, we can assert the existence of pairs of prime numbers, (p_1, p_2) , such that $p_1 + p_2 = 2k - 2i$ for all natural numbers $i < k$.

2. Define the Set of Shifted Primes With this assumption, we define a new set for each even number $2k$,

$$S_{2k} = \{(a, b) \mid a + b = 2k, a, b \in \mathcal{P}\}$$

where $\mathcal{P}$ is the formal set of all prime numbers. We know from the inductive base the existence of pairs that will shift to new "locations" and maintain their prime status, implying the non-emptiness of S_{2k} .

3. Construct the Complement Set Next, we express the set of non-prime odd numbers (possible composites) as a complement set relative to S_{2k} and prime numbers:

$$C_{2k} = \{(a, b) \mid a + b = 2k, a \notin \mathcal{P} \text{ or } b \notin \mathcal{P}\}$$

where C_{2k} must not intersect with S_{2k} within our formal logic space.

4. Utilize Counting Argument The document implies that the total number of locations from shifted prime pairs will exceed the total number of locations available for $2k$. This implies a contradiction because we cannot have more location pairs than the ones derived from S_{2k} . We can state this formally as,

$$|S_{2k}| \geq \Delta P_{2k}$$

where ΔP_{2k} is the count of all shifted prime pairs inherited from prior verified cases up to $2k - 2$.

5. Reductio ad Absurdum Assume that S_{2k} is empty, meaning there are no two primes that sum to $2k$. This leads to a contradiction with the computed ΔP_{2k} , which guarantees the presence of prime pairs due to the shifting mechanism. This contradiction implies our assumption is false, and S_{2k} must be non-empty.

6. Final Inference By demonstrating that S_{2k} is non-empty for any chosen $2k$, and given the inductive hypothesis that all previous cases have been true, we have shown that Goldbach's conjecture holds for $2k$, completing the inductive step.

Conclusion: Synthesizing the set-theoretical approach with the counting argument from the document results in an inductive framework suggesting that, assuming Goldbach's conjecture holds for all cases up to $2k - 2$, a contradiction arises when assuming it fails for $2k$. Thus, the conjecture must be true for $2k$ as well.

However, it is crucial to note that this outlined approach and the proof structure provided require rigorous verification and formal mathematical scrutiny, as they are highly abstract and presented without the detailed demonstrations needed for a conclusive proof. Given the historical difficulty of proving Goldbach's conjecture, a true proof would need to be published and peer-reviewed within the mathematical community for validation and confirmation.

References

- [1] Dorostanian, Amin. "A Proof of Goldbach's Conjecture." arXiv:1905.08033, May 2019.
- [2] Emmerson, Parker. "Three Methods for Testing Goldbach's Conjecture (with Python Code)." Zenodo, August 2017, <https://zenodo.org/records/10448186>.
- [3] Emmerson, Parker. "Logic Patterns in Prime Numbers." Zenodo, November 2021, <https://zenodo.org/records/7968860>.